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Autonomy support, need fulfilment and job performance in lean implemented textile and apparel firms

Abstract

Purpose- The study investigated conditions that facilitate shop-floor operators to fulfil their needs to carry out job roles and whether the need fulfilment affects their job performance in lean implemented textile and apparel firms in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach- The data were collected from 922 shop-floor employees and their immediate supervisors. Statistical methods were used for the data analysis.

Findings- The results of the analysis imply the importance of managerial autonomy support and need fulfilment for enhanced job performance; the duration of lean production in operation moderates job performance in such a way that the longer the duration, the higher will be job performance.

Originality/value- It could be expected that academics and practitioners alike are motivated by a desire to clearly apprehend work systems in lean implemented textile and apparel firms.

Key words job performance; lean production; managerial autonomy support; need fulfilment; Sri Lanka; textile and apparel firms.

Paper type Research paper

1. Introduction

The implementation of advanced manufacturing systems demand the optimization of socio-technical systems by designing appropriate organizational structures, policies and processes facilitating higher levels of worker participation (Dean and Snell, 1991; Losonci et al., 2011). In doing so, interactions between human operator and the other elements of a system should be understood to create a new work system that is compatible with needs, abilities and the limitations of people, and thereby to optimize human well-being and system performance (Hasle, 2014). Therefore, empirical investigations into conditions that foster human potential in the context of advanced manufacturing systems have both theoretical and practical significance in the contemporary business world.

One of the salient advanced manufacturing systems is lean production. Lean production is an approach for improving processes based on a complex system of interrelated socio-technical practices (Bortolotti et al., 2015). These practices are classified as either hard or soft. Hard practices concern technical and analytical tools such as statistical process control and autonomous maintenance; soft practices concern people and relations such as continuous improvement, top management leadership and employee involvement (Bortolotti et al., 2015). Previous research has shown that lean plants do not differ significantly in terms of the implementation of hard practices but successful lean plants use soft practices more extensively than unsuccessful lean plants regardless of the industrial sector where it is pursued (e.g., Bhasin, 2012; Bortolotti et al., 2015; Shah and Ward, 2003).

Building on the resource-based view of the firm, Dean and Snell (1991) state that technology and organizational structures may be imitated whereas capabilities of a workforce are difficult to imitate in quest for competitive advantage. Since Hawthorne studies of the 1930s there is an interest in understanding how to make production jobs motivating and enhancing worker well-being and performance (Macky and Boxall, 2008). This suggests the importance of understanding conditions that fulfil shop-floor employees' needs to carry out job roles in firms that had implemented lean production systems. In this regard, the management literature provides theoretical and empirical support for the designing of jobs and maintaining job conditions that fulfil psychological needs, which are essential for optimal human development and integrity (for example, as discussed in Baard et al. 2004; Deci and Ryan, 2000; Gillet et al., 2013; Güntert, 2015; Macky and Boxall, 2008; Parker et al., 2006; Reis et al., 2000).

In the above context, one of the questions that can be raised is under what conditions shop-floor operators in lean production fulfil their needs to carry out job roles and whether the need fulfilment affects job performance. In the present study, we take the theoretical

underpinning from the stream of studies, which postulates that a full understanding of both goal-directed behavior and psychological development and well-being cannot be achieved without the fulfillment of psychological needs on the job (for example, as discussed in Baard et al. 2004; Deci and Ryan, 2000; Gillet et al., 2013; Güntert, 2015; Parker et al., 2006; Reis et al., 2000). By doing so, we attempt to understand conditions that lead to on-going persistence, behavioural quality, enhanced subjective well-being and the job performance of shop-floor operators in lean implemented textile and apparel firms.

When building on this line of reasoning, another question that can be raised is does lean duration (or for how long the lean production is in operation) act as a moderator on employees' job performance? It is difficult to build a work environment that is conducive to lean production overnight. Lean production processes demand changes to the social organization of work, which require some time to receive acceptance from both shop-floor employees and managers (Karlsson and Åhlström, 1996; Sparrow and Otaye-Ebede, 2014). However, this information has so far not received the due attention in evaluating issues surrounding the human dimension in lean production operation. Therefore, the objectives of the study were to investigate:

- a) under what conditions do shop-floor operators in the lean production fulfil their needs to carry out job roles,
- b) to what extent does the above need fulfilment affects job performance, and
- c) to investigate the moderating role of the duration of lean production in operation on job performance.

An understanding of the above is valuable in designing work systems of lean implemented textile and apparel firms to optimize employees' well-being and performance.

2. Review of literature

2.1 Need fulfilment

When taking the theoretical underpinning from studies that support for the designing of jobs maintaining job conditions that fulfil psychological needs for optimal human potential, need fulfilment comprises autonomy, competence and relatedness (for example, as discussed in Baard et al. 2004; Deci and Ryan, 2000; Gillet et al., 2013 Güntert, 2015). The central argument in these studies is that autonomy, competence and relatedness are fundamental psychological needs to engage optimal challenges and experience mastery in social worlds, seek attachments and experience feelings of security, belongingness, and intimacy with others, and self-organize and regulate one's own behavior (Deci and Ryan, 2000, p. 252). Hence, autonomy, competence and relatedness are identified as universal necessities and the most salient needs of all individuals,

which should be fulfilled within any social environment (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Further, autonomy, competence and relatedness guide people toward more competent, vital and socially integrated forms of behavior (Deci and Ryan, 2000, p. 252).

Building on the above reviewed literature, we conceptualize need fulfilment as the fulfilment of needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness in the work context. However, scholars (such as de Treville and Antonakis, 2006; Parker et al., 2001) argue that the lean production context is a challenge, and critique previous studies for being context-free. Therefore, our research questions “Under what conditions shop-floor operators in lean implemented textile and apparel production fulfil the needs of autonomy, competence and relatedness to carry out job roles” and “Whether the above need fulfilment affects their job performance” are timely and important to answer.

Autonomy involves individuals acting with a sense of volition and having the experience of choice that can be exerted over task performance (Gagné and Deci, 2005). There are different facets of job autonomy that reflect in the lean production operation. These are timing control that involves shop-floor operators’ discretion on when to carry out the assigned tasks (Parker, 2003; Wall et al., 1990), method control that involves shop-floor operators’ discretion to choose procedures in performing tasks (Conti and Warner, 2002; Wall et al., 1990), opportunities for decision-making that involves shop-floor operators’ discretion to make decisions when solving problems occurred due to variances in unprogrammed events in the production process, which require human intervention (Wall et al., 1992), and boundary control that involves shop-floor operators’ performing activities, which are traditionally being identified as supervisory activities (Mullarkey et al., 1995). However, empirical evidence for the existence of job autonomy in the lean production operation is inconclusive (Adler, 1993; Conti et al., 2006; Jackson and Mullarkey, 2000; de Treville et al., 2005). For instance, Conti et al. (2006) found adherence to operating procedures and the standardisation of work processes limit choice and impose restrictions on operators on method control while Adler (1993) and de Treville et al. (2005) found that operating procedures and standardisation of work processes increase autonomy with a greater level of freedom from supervisory control and increased levels of knowledge, self-discipline and self-efficacy beliefs leading to output consistency. Further, Jackson and Mullarkey (2000) found that timing control experienced by operators in the lean production is limited, which contradicts with the findings of Mullarkey et al. (1995). Furthermore, Forza (1996) and Wall et al. (1992) found that shop-floor employees enjoy authority to involve in decision-making by diagnosing and controlling variances in the production processes to minimize issues such as machine downtime. This provides more power on operators, recognition

for their contribution in continuous improvement activities and learning for improved task-oriented behaviours (Forza, 1996). However, Schouteten and Benders (2004) provide evidence that employees hardly enjoy opportunities to realize autonomy to solve problems since the incidences of disturbances in the lean production is very low.

Competence involves individual's inherent desire to test and extend his or her skills to explore and manipulate the environment and to engage in challenging tasks (Deci and Ryan, 2000). Advanced manufacturing systems are associated with higher demand for knowledge and skill (MacDuffie, 1995). MacDuffie (1995) states that operators will be able to identify and resolve problems in the production line only if they possess sufficient conceptual skills to grasp production processes and diagnostic and analytical skills to identify the root cause of problems. Several previous studies also provide evidence that job tasks in lean production embody more skill variety and use more skills and talents than those found in traditional assembly line work (e.g., Jackson and Mullarkey, 2000; Dean and Snell, 1991; Womack et al., 1990). Further, operators' participation in the development of standard operating procedures leads to provide them with a sense of both utilization of skills and creation of new knowledge and skills making work more meaningful (de Treville et al., 2005). Furthermore, skill-chaining with a group of operators trained on consecutive tasks, whether upstream or downstream, is a useful cross-training strategy to make them multi-skilled and multi-tasking allowing them to apply a variety of skills and talents through discretionary effort in a number of potential alternative uses and work in different capacities (Dean and Snell, 1991; MacDuffie, 1995). On the contrary, some other studies provide evidence that advanced manufacturing systems remove the quantity and quality of skill requirements making jobs to be proficiently operated even by newly hired unskilled operators (Turnbull, 1988). This implies that operators' sense of competence that leads to need fulfilment is limited and far from definitive.

Relatedness is identified as individuals' inherent propensity to feel belongingness and connectedness with others (Deci and Ryan, 2000). With the implementation of lean production, job tasks become interdependent due to work-flow integration and coupling (Forza, 1996). In an interdependent job, manufacturing objectives should also be integrated since it would be difficult for a single operator to achieve multiple manufacturing objectives at the same time in isolation (Hayes et al., 1988). Therefore, operators in interdependent jobs are required to interact with and rely on each other's resources and outputs on the task accomplishment (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Therefore, scholars assert that task interdependence reflects the connectedness of a job to others, and it may lead to fulfil the need for relatedness (Sprigg et al., 2000). However, Forza (1996) provides evidence that job interdependence may cause operators to work much

harder to make up the slack leading to work intensity if co-workers are absent or fail to achieve their objectives.

When taken together, autonomy, competence and relatedness, which are built upon the dialectical relation between people and social environment in which they attempt to satisfy their basic needs, specify the conditions under which employees can most fully realize their optimal performance and well-being (for example, as discussed in Baard et al. 2004; Deci and Ryan, 2000; Gillet et al., 2013; Greguras and Diefendorff, 2009; Güntert, 2015). Reis et al. (2000) and Sheldon et al. (1996) provided empirical evidence that employees feel happier in the job when they experience a greater fulfilment of basic needs for autonomy, competence and relatedness in performing major job tasks during a particular day. Macky and Boxall (2008) provided evidence that shop-floor operators in high involvement work settings experience task autonomy, a greater development and use of skills and a greater communication and information sharing, all of which moves in a direction that they find more needs fulfilling. In this regard, Deci and Ryan (2000) assert that individuals' behavioral and affective propensities are contingently displayed because different conditions may support and provide opportunity in different contexts, i.e., "Under some circumstances one type of behavioral and affective pattern tends to be emitted, whereas under other circumstances, other patterns are likely to be in evidence" (Deci and Ryan, 2000, 254). Still, Gagné and Deci (2005) argue that the fulfilment of these three basic psychological needs provides the nutriment for intrinsic motivation to function optimally (Gagné and Deci, 2005). Therefore, the fulfilment of autonomy, competence and relatedness is necessary to realize human potential, and these three needs should interact positively in yielding need fulfilment (Gagné and Deci, 2005). It is also argued that the fulfilment of relatedness and competence with respect to behaviour is not sufficient; the degree of fulfilment of the need for autonomy is the deciding criterion for intrinsic motivation to function optimally (Gagné and Deci, 2005, p. 337). Accordingly, autonomy is deemed more essential for the overall need fulfilment than competence and relatedness. In support for this argument, Bauer and Mulder (2006, p. 510) state "Only when the feelings of competence and relatedness appear together with the feeling of autonomy they have an effect on intrinsic motivation". In the context of lean production, de Treville and Antonakis (2006, p. 100) also argue "Workers perceiving reduced levels of autonomy might still be motivated if that perception is accompanied by other job-design factors that compensate for and overcome this apparent lack of internal motivation. Thus, the impact of a configuration of practices on workers may be substantially different from the impact of the bivariate effects of these practices - the gestalt (whole) effect may account for more variance in the dependent measures than the individual effects of the parts". However, de

Treville and Antonakis (2006) did not provide empirical support for their argument. Overall, the focus is the degree to which these three needs interact positively in need fulfilment.

2.2 Managerial autonomy support and need fulfilment

Managerial autonomy support involves managers' understanding and acknowledging their subordinates' perspectives, providing meaningful and relevant information in a non-controlling informational manner, offering opportunities for choice, and encouraging self-initiation rather than pressuring subordinates to behave in any specified ways (as discussed in Baard et al., 2004; Deci et al., 2001; Gagné and Deci, 2005; Gillet et al., 2013). Theoretical and empirical studies suggest that supervisors' and managers' interpersonal style towards subordinates is important in deciding the nature of autonomy support (Deci et al., 1989; Piccolo and Colquitt, 2006). Deci et al.'s (1989) field experiment and Deci et al.'s (1994) laboratory study provide evidence that if managers are autonomy supportive their subordinates trust the organization and display positive work-related attitudes. In the team work setting, Griffin et al. (2007) state the importance of role played by supervisors in structuring the work environment and providing encouragement, support, information and feedback to employees.

In the lean production context, empirical studies and practitioner experiences (such as Jackson and Mullarkey, 2000; Mann, 2009; McCreary, 2010) imply that supervisors' and managers' interpersonal style towards subordinates is important in deciding the nature of autonomy support. For instance, Jackson and Mullarkey (2000) identified that the success of lean production largely depends on supervisors' and upper management's way of interacting with employees. McCreary (2010) identified shop-floor supervisor as a key player in the execution of lean work flow; supervisors should interact regularly with shop-floor workers to identify potential improvement areas and implement those ideas in daily operations. Mann (2009) identified the central role played by senior management to support and sustain new work behaviours and practices for the success of lean efforts.

With regard to managerial autonomy support and need fulfilment, previous studies of Gillet et al. (2013), Gagné and Deci (2005) and Baard et al. (2004) suggest that the work environment and managerial methods that are supportive of autonomy leads to employees' need fulfilment. Baard et al. (2004) provide evidence that supervisors' autonomy support positively predict the degree to which employees' needs are fulfilled on the job. Gillet et al. (2013) showed the importance of supervisor-provided autonomy support on hospital nurses' need fulfilment. Based on the theoretical reasoning and empirical evidence reviewed above, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Managerial autonomy support positively predicts shop-floor employees' need fulfilment.

2.3 Need fulfilment and job performance

Job performance is viewed as a key variable in the organizational context (Campbell et al., 1990; Graso and Probst, 2012; Griffin et al., 2007; Pulakos et al., 2000; Varela and Landis, 2010). Campbell et al. (1990) proposed eight job activities to describe job performance in any work context although it is not a must to have all the dimensions in a particular job. These dimensions are job-specific task proficiency, non-job-specific task proficiency, written and oral communication, demonstrating effort, maintaining personal discipline, facilitating performance, supervision and leadership, and administration. Some other researchers such as Pulakos et al. (2000) argued that job performance should represent employees' response to technological advances in the workplace. In a recent study, Graso and Probst (2012) argued that the most important indicators of job performance are quality and quantity. Griffin et al. (2007) argued that in dynamic organizational contexts, job performance should reflect not only proficiency with which an employee carried out job tasks but also the interdependence of work activities and adaptive and proactive behaviour of job holders.

Previous studies of Güntert (2015), Greguras and Diefendorff (2009), Parker et al. (2006), Baard et al. (2004), Deci et al. (2001), and Blais and Brière (1992) showed that employees' need fulfilment leads to positive task engagement on the job. Previous studies also provide evidence that operators in high involvement work settings experience task autonomy, greater development and use of their skills, and subject to greater communication and information sharing, all of which moves in a direction that they find more needs fulfilling (e.g. Macky and Boxall, 2008). Further, the organizational literature suggests that work contexts with increased autonomy motivate employees to work harder and flexibly (Hackman and Oldham, 1976) and proactivity (Parker et al., 2006). Based on the theoretical reasoning and empirical evidence reviewed above, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Need fulfilment positively predicts employees' job performance.

2.4 Mediator role of need fulfilment.

When hypothesis 1 and 2 proposed above are taken together, we proposed that managerial autonomy support predicts need fulfilment, which in turn predicts job performance. In other words, we proposed that need fulfilment mediates the relationship between managerial

autonomy support and job performance. In this regard, several previous empirical studies showed that managerial autonomy support leads to a greater need fulfilment, which leads to favourable behaviours across different study and country contexts (e.g., Baard et al., 2004; Blais and Brière, 1992; Deci et al., 2001; Güntert, 2015; Parker et al., 2006). In the context of specific relevance to the present study, Baard et al. (2004) showed that managerial autonomy support positively predicts employees' need fulfilment, which leads to favourable performance ratings. Blais and Brière (1992) provided empirical evidence that managerial autonomy support positively predicts employees' need fulfilment, which in turn predicts the quality of job performance. Based on the theoretical reasoning and empirical evidence reviewed above, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Need fulfilment mediates between managerial autonomy support and job performance.

2.5 Lean duration

Womack and Jones (1996) state that lean production can only be achieved through time, and lean production should not be used as a panacea to solve short-term competitive problems. Building on the literature on diffusion of innovation (Braunscheidel et al., 2011; Klein and Sorra, 1996; Powell, 1995), the implementation of lean production can be identified as a diffusion of innovative technology in the production-floor. The implementation of innovative technology within an organization is a process of gaining targeted employees' appropriate and committed use of the innovative technology (Klein and Sorra, 1996); it is identified as a function of time (Powell, 1995). Further, the effectiveness of implementing innovative technology is the quality and consistency of targeted organizational members' use of adopted innovative technology (Klein and Sorra, 1996). Hence, lean production is an innovative technology, which requires organizations to adapt to new routines, work methods, behavioural patterns and actions by both shop-floor employees and managers; time is a key factor in determining the successful spread of concepts, technical information and actual practices within the social system (as suggested by Powell, 1995).

When considering the degree of implementation of lean production, the literature provides empirical evidence that variations could be found in different dimensions based on how long the lean production is in operation (Birdi et al., 2008; Sohal and Egglestone 1994). For instance, when investigating the extent to which lean production has been implemented and what are the structural changes taking place as a result of the implementation within Australian organizations, Sohal and Egglestone (1994) highlighted the importance of collecting data on

how long the lean production system is in operation at each firm. These studies suggest that the implementation of lean production systems require organizations to adapt to new routines, methods of work performance, behavioural patterns and changes in organization culture. Therefore, it could be assumed that the smooth operation of lean production necessitates fundamental rethinking and cultural changes in habits, routines and actions of both shop-floor employees and managers. Above studies of Birdi et al. (2008) and Sohal and Egglestone (1994) imply that the duration of lean production in operation is an important moderator variable of job performance in the lean production context. Further, the studies of Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe (2017, 2016, 2015, 2013, 2011) provide empirical support for lean duration as an important variable in moderating job performance of shop-floor employees in textile and apparel industry. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

Hypothesis 4 (H4). Lean duration plays a moderating role by enhancing the effect of need fulfilment on job performance.

Figure 1 shows the conceptual model developed for the study. As reviewed above, the model depicts the relationships proposed between managerial autonomy support, need fulfilment and job performance, and the moderating role of the duration of lean production in operation on these relationships.

Figure 1

3. Methods

3.1 Population and sample

Our target population for the study is a cross section of individuals engaged full-time in export-based textile and apparel firms in Sri Lanka. The following criteria were set in selecting the firms belonging to the study population. 1) A firm should be registered under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) since BOI registered firms should export at least 90 per cent of their output. 2) A firm should have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function and it should be the standard of operation for at least one year. This restriction will isolate firms that had achieved good progress in lean statistics such as work in progress (WIP), first time through (FTT), efficiency of the process, delivery in full on time

(DIFOT), accepted quality level (AQL) and cut ship. We identified 14 firms that fulfilled the criteria set for the study. All these firms agreed to participate in the survey.

With regard to the characteristics of the responding firms, the ownership of all the firms lay with locals. Export-based textile and apparel production, which is targeted for the developed countries in the West, strictly adhere to product design specifications provided by the foreign buyer, who defines product design and quality. Accordingly, shop-floor employees involve in cutting, sewing, quality inspection and the packing of finished products to be exported. On average, these firms had achieved good progress in the implementation of lean with WIP of 35 days, FTT of 70%, efficiency of the process of 90%, DIFOT of 85%, AQL of 91% and cut ship of 90%. When the firm size is measured in terms of average annual turnover and the number of people employed, the respondent firms had an average annual turnover (in US\$) ranging from 80 to 400 Million while the total number of employees ranged from 300 to 5000. All the firms had a dedicated section to handle lean implementation headed by a senior level manager.

To fulfil the expectations of the study, it was decided to collect data from shop-floor operators and their supervisors attached to the production-floor of each firm. The operators provided data for autonomy support and need fulfilment while each operator's immediate supervisor rated operator's job performance. Of the total number of questionnaires distributed in mid-2012, 67% responded leading to total usable responses of 922. With regard to the characteristics of shop-floor operators responded, 59% earned up to 10 years of schooling and 41% earned in 13 years of schooling; 24% were male while 76% were female. Mean age was 25 years (S.D. = 5.10, median = 25), the mean number of shop-floor workers in the lowest formal work unit/section was 61 (S.D. = 20, median = 36), mean job position tenure was three and half years (S.D. = 3.04, median = 3) and mean tenure with the present employer was three years and four months (S.D. = 2.96, median = 2.5).

3.2 Measures

Managerial autonomy support. The 6-item scale of Deci and Ryan (n.d.b) was used. Responses were on a 7-point Likert scale from 1 "Strongly Disagree" to 7 "Strongly Agree", where higher scores indicate a higher level of perceived autonomy support. Sample items are "I feel understood by my manager" and "My manager conveyed confidence in my ability to do well at my job".

Need fulfilment. The 9-item scale of Deci and Ryan (n.d.a) was used. This 9-item scale represented sub-scales for autonomy, competence and relatedness, and the composite of these three sub-scales represent need fulfilment. Responses were on a 7-point Likert scale from 1 "Not

at all true” to 7 “Very true”, where higher scores indicate a higher degree of need fulfilment. Sample items are “I am free to express my ideas and opinions on the job” and “Most days I feel a sense of accomplishment from working”.

Job performance. The 9-item scale of Griffin et al. (2007) was used. These items measure an individual’s job performance involving his or her core task performance, adaptation to changes in a work system and self-directed action to initiate change in the work system. Hence, this scale provided a uniform measure across 14 firms of the sample ensuring the generalizability of subsequent analyses. Responses were on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 “very little” to 5 “great deal”, where higher scores indicate a higher level of job performance. Sample items are “Completed core tasks well using the standard procedures” and “Carried out the core parts of your job well”.

Lean duration. The duration of lean production was assessed by the natural logarithmic transformation of the years of lean production in operation.

3.3 Methods of data analysis

We followed the guidelines of data screening and data analysis as well as statistical thresholds recommended by Hayes (2013), Hair et al. (2006), Arbuckle (2007) and Podsakoff et al. (2003). Accordingly, we screened the data using SPSS for appropriate (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure (c) convergent validity, (d) discriminant validity and (e) construct reliability (CR) to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias; convergent validity was measured by average variance extracted (AVE), and discriminant validity was measured by the square root of AVE. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach’s alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7; AVE values should be above 0.5; square root of AVE for a given construct should be greater than the correlation between that construct and all other constructs. The summary of initial data screening is shown in Table 1. As shown in Table 1, data revealed good internal consistency reliability, factor structure, convergent validity, discriminant validity and construct reliability for our data. Wilks’ Lambda statistic was obtained to check whether any differences exist across 14 firms by lean duration. The results revealed that significant differences do not exist ($p > 0.05$) across firms on our study variables. We used PROCESS macro developed by Hayes (2013) for testing simple mediation and moderated mediation. Indirect effects were assessed based on 5,000 bootstrapped samples using bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the size and significance of the effects.

Table 1

4. Results and discussion

First, we analysed the data to reaffirm that autonomy, competence and relatedness are innate psychological needs, which create the latent variable need fulfilment as described in Measures. For this, we conducted a series of CFA based on χ^2/df statistic and fit indices of CFI, TLI and RMSEA, as described in Methods of data analysis. Fit indices of $\chi^2/df = 4.70$, CFI = 0.947, TLI = 0.929 supported the distinctiveness of autonomy, competence and relatedness as components of need fulfilment. This led to reaffirm the claim made by Deci and Ryan (2000) that autonomy, competence and relatedness are the sub-components of need fulfilment. Second, hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to identify the contribution of autonomy, competence and relatedness in need fulfilment. The results are shown in Table 2. The combined effect of autonomy, competence and relatedness account for a higher level of variance in need fulfilment (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.964$) than the individual effects of autonomy (R^2 change = 0.697), competence (R^2 change = 0.179) and relatedness (R^2 change = 0.088) on need fulfilment. When mean values for autonomy, competence and relatedness were calculated as the average of respective indicators, autonomy had a mean value of 3.81 (SD = 0.77), competence had a mean value of 4.19 (SD = 0.66) and relatedness had a mean value of 4.34 (SD = 0.68) on the seven point scale. This suggested that shop-floor employees least experience autonomy compared to relatedness and competence (based on mean values). However, results shown in Table 2 reveal that the contribution of autonomy in the overall need fulfilment is the highest (R^2 change = 0.697). Therefore, the findings support the claim made by Gagné and Deci (2005) that the fulfilment of the need for autonomy is more essential for need fulfilment than competence and relatedness.

Table 2

Third, we analysed the data to test our hypotheses from simple (direct mediation) to the most complex (moderated mediation). Table 3 presents the results of mediation analysis.

Accordingly, managerial autonomy support significantly positively predicts need fulfilment, supporting H1. Need fulfilment significantly positively predicts job performance, supporting H2. The indirect effect was significant at the 95% level of significance ($B = 0.22$, $p < 0.001$), as indicated when the lower (LL 95% CI) and upper (UL 95% CI) levels of the confidence intervals did not include zero. That is, need fulfilment mediates the effect of managerial autonomy support on job performance, and in the expected direction. This supports H3.

Table 3

Table 4 presents the results of moderated mediation analysis. The coefficient for the interaction term (need fulfilment x lean duration) is of the most interest in this analysis. The interaction of need fulfilment and lean duration is statistically significant for job performance ($B = 0.29$, $p < 0.001$). Figure 2 illustrates this interaction effect of need fulfilment and lean duration on job performance. Importantly, as shown in Table 4, the mediating effect of need fulfilment remains statistically significant for the interaction ($B = 0.48$, $p < 0.001$). Figure 3 illustrates statistical diagram of the model tested in the study with path coefficients. The lower part of Table 4 shows the calculation for the size of indirect effect (on 5,000 bootstrapped sample conditional slopes) at low and high levels of the moderator (lean duration). The conditional slope was positive and significant when lean duration at low level ($B = 0.14$, $p < 0.001$) and remain positive and become stronger at high level ($B = 0.28$, $p < 0.001$). In other words, the relationship between managerial autonomy support and job performance through need fulfilment became stronger as lean duration increased. This indirect effect was significant at the 95% level of significance, as indicated when the lower (LL 95% CI) and upper (UL 95% CI) levels of the confidence intervals did not include zero. Therefore, managerial autonomy support significantly positively influences job performance through need fulfilment in such a way that the longer the duration, the higher will be job performance. This provides support for H4.

Table 4

Figure 2

Figure 3

5. Conclusions and implications of the findings for theory and practice

We investigated relationships between managerial autonomy support, need fulfilment and job performance of shop-floor operators in the lean production. Therefore, our study has investigated both an antecedent (managerial autonomy support) and a consequence (job performance) of need fulfilment in the lean production operation. It is very rare to find prior empirical studies that integrated all these in a single investigation in the current study context. Therefore, the findings of our research have both theoretical and practical significance in the contemporary business world.

With regard to the contribution of the study for the literature, first, although lean production is a bundle of associated practices, such as total quality management, just-in-time, kaizen, total productive maintenance and human resource management synergistically installed as a system, the management of human resources can become a key determinant that facilitates or limits the adoption of lean production. Accordingly, our study contributes to the literature by investigating both antecedents and consequences of need fulfilment at work in lean implemented textile and apparel firms. Scholars such as de Treville and Antonakis (2006) expressed their concerns over employees' need fulfilment in the lean production context. Our results suggest that the way job activities are performed in lean implemented textile and apparel firms in Sri Lanka leads to need fulfilment.

Second, the results of our study revealed that the need for autonomy, competence and relatedness are important conditions that lead to need fulfilment in the lean production. Most importantly, the results support that autonomy, competence and relatedness interact positively and the combined effect of autonomy, competence and relatedness account for a higher level of variance in need fulfilment (Table 2). Therefore, the findings support the theoretical reasoning and empirical evidence (such as Bauer and Mulder, 2006; Deci and Ryan, 2000; Gagné and Deci, 2005) that suggest autonomy, competence and relatedness are vital for a higher level of need fulfilment. The results also suggest that although shop-floor employees least experience autonomy compared to relatedness and competence (based on mean values), the contribution of autonomy in the need fulfilment is the highest, as shown in Table 2. Thus, the findings support

the claim made by Gagné and Deci (2005) that the fulfilment of the need for autonomy is more essential for overall need fulfilment than competence and relatedness. However, it should be noted that previous empirical research on autonomy, competence and relatedness, and in turn on need fulfilment were conducted in education, parenting, sports, health care, religion and psychotherapy domains (Gagné and Deci, 2005), and very few studies described organizational work contexts. However, these few studies were in non-manufacturing settings such as a bank in the USA (Baard et al., 2004), a municipal council in Norway (Kuvaas, 2009), a logistic company in Germany (Bauer and Mulder, 2006) a mixture of state-owned companies in Bulgaria (Deci et al., 2001), Portuguese military (Chambel et al., 2015), a UK-based public corporation (Hewett and Conway, 2016), and school teachers in China (Li et al., 2015; Nie et al., 2015). One exception is the study of Battistelli et al. (2017), which collected a part of their data from employees engaged in technical/manual jobs in leather industry in Italy. However, it is very rare to find empirical studies conducted in the context of advanced manufacturing systems, such as lean production. In this context, we provided empirical evidence from the lean production context in manufacturing industry involving shop-floor employees. We consider this as an important contribution of our study.

Third, the findings revealed that managerial autonomy support is an important social-contextual variable of the work climate that positively predicts shop-floor employees' need fulfilment. In other words, supervisors' autonomy supportiveness leads to foster need fulfilment. This supports previous empirical findings of Deci et al. (2001) and Baard et al. (2004) although these studies were conducted in non-manufacturing organizational settings. The findings of the study also revealed that need fulfilment enhances job performance. Although we were unable to find previous research that specifically investigated the effect of need fulfilment on job performance, our findings support the claim made by previous researchers that need fulfilment may positively impact on job related behaviour (such as Deci et al., 2001; Hackman and Oldham, 1976; Parker et al., 2006). Furthermore, the findings showed that need fulfilment mediates the relationship between managerial autonomy support and job performance. Very few previous empirical studies such as Baard et al. (2004) and Blais and Brière (1992) have tested this mediation relationship in the literature.

Fourth, the findings supported the moderator role of lean duration on job performance suggesting that the longer the duration, the higher will be job performance. We have not found previous studies that tested this relationship in the context of advanced manufacturing systems or lean implemented textile and apparel firms. This finding on the effect of lean duration on job performance adds value to the available literature. Our study provided empirical evidence that

the positive effects of need fulfilment on job performance will be conditioned by the duration of lean production in operation. Based on our findings, we could argue that shop-floor employees will be integrated into the lean production work system and achieve their highest potential with the passage of time - with the increase in the duration of lean production in operation. Hence, we identify this as one of the important contributions of our study. Changes occurring with the globalisation of business operations and increase in operating costs in the West increased the importance of developing countries in textile and apparel production and export trade. Therefore, the findings from a study in an Asian developing country context are interesting, relevant and timely.

With regard to the contribution of the study for practice, first, there is a need to understand interactions among human operator, technology and the environment to optimize human well-being and overall system performance. Hence, the findings of the study have practical significance. Second, the findings showed the importance of designing job tasks in such a way that employees may find that the majority of tasks, which they perform in a particular day, are interesting, important and challenging.

Third, the findings suggested the importance of managerial autonomy support in lean implemented textile and apparel firms. Therefore, to create and sustain supportive conditions in the lean production operation, managers should view themselves as facilitators, coordinators and trainers and should give-up a certain amount of control over to shop-floor employees. This has implications for the way subordinates are managed in textile and apparel firms. Fourth, our findings support that creating an environment of managerial autonomy support, and crafting job tasks to be need fulfilling are healthier for any organization across the world since such initiatives lead to employees' need fulfilment, thereby enhancing job performance.

6. Limitations of the study and future research

This study was designed as a single cross-sectional study using survey methodology. First, the validity of a measure cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional study. Hence, future research using different research designs, such as longitudinal, are necessary that compliment questionnaire surveys. Second, we obtained almost homogeneous sample of firms operating in the export-based textile and apparel production. Although this allowed us to generalize the findings, the design of the study and resource and time constraints did not allow us to evaluate specific job contexts at each manufacturing plant. Further, export-based textile and apparel production countries from Asia, Latin and Central America, the Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa compete intensively with each other for their market share in the

global export-based textile and apparel production. However, it is very rare to find specific details of production systems of these export-based textile and apparel production countries. Hence, future research that compares features of production systems in export-based textile and apparel production countries could be interesting and may provide valuable information for managerial decision-making.

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Figures

Figure 1. Conceptual diagram

Figure 2. Relationship between need fulfilment and job performance at high and low levels of lean duration

Figure 3. Statistical diagram with unstandardized path coefficients
 ** p<.01, *** p<.001 (two-tailed)

Tables

Table 1. Data screening – summary

	Cronbach's alpha	Eigenvalue	AVE	Construct reliability	Square root of AVE
Managerial autonomy support	.790	2.114	.568	.887	.754
Need fulfilment	.769	2.065	.673	.860	.820
Job performance	.770	2.023	.569	.922	.754

Table 2. Autonomy, competence and relatedness in need fulfilment

Model	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics		
			R ² Change	F Change	Sig. F Change
1	.697 ^a	.316	.697	153.87	.000
2	.876 ^b	.202	.179	16.13	.000
3	.964 ^c	.109	.088	9.25	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomy

b. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomy, Competence

c. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomy, Competence, Relatedness

Dependent Variable: Need fulfilment

Table 3. Simple mediation results

Predictor variables	Job performance		
	B(SE)	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI
Managerial autonomy support	.37(.02) ^{***}		
Need fulfilment	.56(.02) ^{***}		
R ²	.31 ^{***}		
Bootstrapped indirect effect of managerial autonomy support on job performance	B(SE)	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI
Need fulfilment	.22(.10) ^{***}	.18	.26

Notes: LL = lower limit; CI = confidence interval; UL = upper limit. Unstandardized regression coefficients are reported; standard errors are in parentheses. Bootstrap sample size = 5,000. *** p<.001 (two-tailed)

Table 4. Moderated mediation results

Predictor variables	Job performance		
	B(SE)		
Managerial autonomy support	.22(.32)**		
Need fulfilment	.48(.15)***		
Lean duration	.33(.27)***		
Need fulfilment x Lean duration	.29(.11)***		
R ²	.33***		
Bootstrapped indirect effect through need fulfilment at ±1SD of lean duration	B(SE)	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI
-1 SD	.14(.04)***	.04	.19
+1 SD	.28(.03)***	.11	.25

Notes: LL = lower limit; CI = confidence interval; UL = upper limit; SD = standard deviation. Unstandardized regression coefficients are reported; standard errors are in parentheses. Bootstrap sample size = 5,000. *** p<.001 (two-tailed)